

Salar Heritage Community Membership Agreement

Heritage unites us, community strengthens us.

Heritage is not only what we inherit, but what we decide to care
for together.

1. Salar Heritage Community (Granada)

The creation of a Heritage Community is a key tool for protecting, valuing and revitalising the cultural and natural heritage of a territory by its own inhabitants.

This concept stems from the Faro Convention (Council of Europe, 2005), which defines a heritage community as: a group of people who value specific aspects of cultural heritage that they wish to maintain and pass on to future generations within the framework of public action.

Salar is a territory with an extraordinary concentration of heritageS

Its strategic location in the Vega of Granada, next to the Genil River and ancient historic roads, has favoured continuous human occupation from prehistoric times to the present day. This long process has given rise to a rich cultural landscape, where nature, water, agriculture and history intertwine.

The municipality preserves an outstanding hydraulic heritage, thanks to the availability of different water resources: the Salar stream and historic springs such as Fuente Alta, El Bañuelo and El Membrillo. These have given rise to traditional water management systems (irrigation channels) that have sustained agricultural life and settlement for centuries.

Added to this is an **exceptional archaeological heritage**, with sites dating from prehistory to the Iberian, Roman and Andalusian periods.

The Roman villa of Salar stands out in particular, as one of the most important archaeological sites in the south of the Iberian peninsula, along with other historical settlements scattered throughout the municipal area.

Salar also has an important historical and architectural heritage, represented by the Andalusian tower, the church of Santa Ana, the historic farmhouses and other elements linked to the evolution of rural settlement.

This complex is complemented by a living **intangible and social cultural heritage**, expressed in the traditions, festivals and celebrations that continue to form part of the local identity, such as **Carnival** or the **Cattle Fair**, as well as in the knowledge, trades and ways of life linked to the agricultural world.

The Salar Heritage Community could therefore be defined as:

An open group of residents, associations, professionals and entities that wish to care for, protect and raise awareness of our historical, cultural, natural and social heritage. The Community is founded on the conviction that heritage is not just a collection of monuments or archaeological remains, but also our traditions, our ways of life, our agricultural knowledge and the landscape that surrounds us.

Each element (from the Roman villa and the Andalusian tower to the springs, irrigation channels, Carnival, Cattle Fair and agricultural life) forms part of a heritage that defines us as a people and deserves to be valued, passed on and enjoyed.

Its main objective is to promote sustainable development based on heritage, through participatory and fair management models that promote the responsible, equitable and respectful use of cultural and natural resources. This means that all members of the Community will be able to participate in decision-making, the organisation of activities, the dissemination of heritage and the creation of new initiatives that benefit the entire population.

In this way, our heritage ceases to be a static resource and becomes an active driver of cultural, social and economic development, open to the participation of the entire community.

2. Purpose of this document

The purpose of this document is to formalise membership of the Salar Heritage Community, expressing a commitment to support, protect and promote our cultural, environmental and natural heritage.

Individuals or entities that join will form part of an open working group that will meet periodically to discuss, make proposals and develop initiatives on the present and future of Salar's heritage, as well as its inhabitants and local businesses.

With this document, we invite neighbours, associations, professionals and educational centres to join the Salar Heritage Community, expressing their commitment to care for, enjoy and promote our heritage. Together we can decide how to protect it and use it for the benefit of all. The heritage community aims to be a formal participatory management tool with decision-making and planning capabilities.

3. Who can join?

The Salar Heritage Community is open to all individuals, groups and institutions that share a commitment to protecting, promoting and disseminating local heritage, including:

- The local community**, including neighbours, families, farmers, irrigators and other agents linked to the territory.
- Associations and groups**, such as cultural associations, women's associations, foundations and local entities.
- Professionals and experts**, such as historians, archaeologists, tour guides, teachers, businesses, trade associations and other professionals linked to heritage, culture and tourism.
- Public institutions**, especially the Salar Town Council, as well as other supra-municipal administrations that may collaborate.
- The educational community**, including schools, colleges and training centres.

The above list is not exhaustive, and any person or entity that shares these values may become part of the Salar Heritage Community.

4. Objectives of the Heritage Community

<p>Participate and collaborate: neighbours, associations and public institutions work together to care for heritage.</p>	<p>Protecting the identity of the people: preventing the loss of traditions and mass tourism.</p>
<p>Keeping heritage alive: traditions, local knowledge and cultural practices remain part of our daily lives</p>	<p>Act as a mechanism for redistributing services and benefits: the resources generated by the heritage are used to strengthen the entire community.</p>
<p>Developing sustainable projects: using heritage as a driver for tourism, education, culture and the local economy.</p>	<p>Strengthening local identity: working together around our heritage reinforces our sense of belonging.</p>

5. Joining commitments

- Participate in and respect community and cultural life.
- Promote cultural, natural and historical heritage.
- Contribute to the conservation and dissemination of heritage.
- Encourage respect and protection of traditions, local knowledge and the natural environment.
- Attend, as far as possible, the meetings and activities of the Heritage Community.

By signing, I join the Salar Heritage Community, committing myself to caring for, valuing and promoting our heritage for present and future generations.

[I WISH TO SIGN THE MEMBERSHIP FORM](#)

